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ONE-YEAR OUTDOOR TESTING OF 4T PEROVSKITE/SI PV MODULES

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ABSTRACT: Perovskite photovoltaics today demonstrate impressive conversion efficiencies, but more field experience is needed to understand their long-term stabilities. Perovskite-on-silicon tandem modules offer a fast-track route to commercialisation, and as such warrant studies of their field performance. This paper reports on the results of a field measurement campaign involving 5 mini tandem modules installed at the University of Cyprus' outdoor test facility. The modules each incorporate a string of seven perovskite sub-cells layered onto a bifacial TOPCON silicon cell, with 4-terminal connections provided to access the individual layers. To reveal trends under stable conditions, data were filtered to use only clear-sky days, which accounted for over 210 days in 20 months of testing. Over the first 12 months of exposure, the perovskite sub-modules showed a 50% reduction in power conversion efficiency (PCE); however, over the following 8 months, they showed either continuous improvement or stable PCE. Over this latter period, the perovskite PCE was not affected by temperature, yet the samples exhibited a stable negative temperature coefficient and a positive fill factor temperature coefficient. An examination of the current-voltage characteristics showed this behaviour likely results from a change in ion mobility with temperature. Overall, the tandem module arrangement has outperformed a single-junction TOPCON device over the test period.

Keywords: Perovskite, Tandem, Outdoor, Modules

1 BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

Perovskite solar cells have demonstrated outstanding performance in recent years, achieving power conversion efficiencies (PCE) as high as 25.5% with theoretical efficiencies calculated up to 31% [1]. Considerable indoor testing has been conducted over recent years at different temperature [2], humidity [3], and bias loading conditions demonstrating the impact of each parameter on the perovskite power conversion efficiency (PCE) and stability. However, while indoor measurements and aging procedures can be used to assess factors impacting stability, they don't fully resemble outdoor operational conditions with regular day-night cycles and continuous changes in irradiance, humidity, and temperature.

Perovskite-on-silicon tandem modules in particular offer advantages as a route to commercialisation of perovskite photovoltaics. Outdoor stability testing of perovskite tandem devices has been reported before [4,5]. It is envisaged that the integration of perovskites into commercially available modules in this manner could involve only a few additional manufacturing steps, and yet would bring all the advantages of high-volume production and supply chains immediately to bear.

Considering the above, the partners of the EU-funded TESTARE project embarked upon a study of the long-term PCE evolution of perovskite/Si tandem miniature modules exposed outdoors for several months.

2 AIM AND APPROACH

The aim of this work is to further the understanding of how tandem solar modules containing a perovskite upper layer on top of a silicon bottom layer perform outdoors over the long term. The central objective of this aim was to collect several years of performance data from a batch of tandem mini modules installed in an outdoor test facility (OTF) with a high annual solar resource. The measurement

campaign started on 19th January 2023 and is still ongoing, with the data up until 1st September 2024 presented in this paper.

2.1 Materials

IMEC prepared a batch of five perovskite-on-silicon tandem mini-modules with dimensions 10 x 10 cm for exposure in the field. Each module contained seven series-connected perovskite sub-cells on a single silicon subcell, as shown in Figure 1. These have a total active area of 4 cm² with a geometrical fill factor of the perovskite layer of approximately 0.91. The encapsulation was achieved by sandwiching the cells between two layers of outer glass with a butyl edge-sealant. A TOPCON technology, bifacial silicon cell with an approximate conversion efficiency of 20% was used, which also accepted additional rear-side-irradiation of the module through the back glass. This module design has been shown to reliably protect the PV cells from moisture and air, which was necessary to ensure that changes in performance over time were not affected by these factors.

Figure 1: Cross-sectional cutaway of the tandem samples, showing the series-connected perovskite layer stack on top of a bifacial silicon cell. A 4-terminal arrangement allowed access to the perovskite and silicon PV contributions independently.

Additionally, a reference mini module containing just the silicon TOPCON cell was prepared. This sample was kept indoors under dark at room temperature and tested regularly over the campaign, yielding a PCE of 21% including a rear-side boost of 5%. Control tandem devices were also prepared and kept indoors for comparison with the field exposed samples.

2.2 Methodology

The five samples were mounted outdoors at the University of Cyprus' outdoor test facility on a south-facing rack tilted at 35 degrees to the horizontal. The test location has a 'Hot-Summer Mediterranean Climate' (Csa) Köppen-Geiger classification, with an approximate annual solar irradiation resource of 2000 kWhm⁻² at optimal tilt. The key irradiation and temperature parameters measured over the test period are summarised in Figure 2.

The global irradiation in the plane of the samples was measured using a silicon reference cell. Module temperatures were measured using PT100 sensors pressed on the rear of three of the modules. Electrical performance parameters of the samples were obtained by regularly sweeping the current-voltage (I-V) curves of each sample over the day. Between each I-V measurement, the samples were left open-circuit. Due to the number of experiments running simultaneously at the test site, only one representative silicon sub-cell was measured outdoors over the full measurement period, from the 506T module.

To measure the module I-V curves, the voltage across the samples was swept from -0.1V to 7.8V and immediately back again. The current was measured at a voltage step of 0.1V with a dwell time at each measurement point of 0.2 seconds. Each sample was measured sequentially roughly every 15 minutes.

Figure 2: Environmental conditions at the University of Cyprus' outdoor test facility recorded over the test period.

Due to the slow response of the perovskite sub-modules to dynamic field conditions, the analyses presented in this paper are performed on data acquired under steady conditions on clear-sky days. These are defined here as days with uninterrupted sunshine characterised by a peak irradiance of over 750 Wm⁻² in the plane of the array, a minimum total daily irradiation exceeding 4.5 kWhm⁻² and a maximum permitted change of irradiance of 200 Wm⁻² over a 15 minute period. At the test site, 123 such days were identified in 2023 and 90 during the first 8 months of 2024. The distribution of these days over the test period is also presented in Figure 2.

3 RESULTS

3.1 PCE over time

The efficiency over time for all the mini modules are plotted together in Figure 3. These values represent monthly average PCE values based on clear-sky days. Generally, the trends of performance seem to fall within three 6-month stages. In the first 6-month period, the PCE of the perovskite subcells is seen to decrease relatively rapidly, to about two-thirds of initial output. In the second 6-month period, the rate of change of PCE seems to halve, as the PCE drops by a further 20% to roughly 50% of initial. However, in the following 6-month period, the performance of the samples seems to plateau and, in some instances, increases.

Figure 3: Monthly average PCE evolution over time for the perovskite subcells, and a silicon subcell. PCE is shown from both forward and reverse sweeps.

The larger scatter in the measurement of the silicon subcell is attributed to the lower current and voltage output compared to the perovskite subcells, and the influence of rear-side irradiance. In all perovskite subcell strings, the reverse sweep showed a higher apparent conversion efficiency due to the presence of hysteresis. The magnitude of the hysteresis over the course of the measurements remains approximately stable at around 1% difference in PCE.

Over the duration of the measurement campaign, it was observed that at certain moments changes in performance were common for several of the samples under test, implying that the cause of these were due to the field conditions. For example, most samples showed an inflection in performance in 2023-08 and again in 2024-02, after which PCE either stabilised or increased. Since these two months are directly preceded by the months with maximum and minimum module temperatures

respectively, there is a suggestion that this could be temperature dependent, but this hypothesis does not hold across the whole data set. During 2024, the perovskite modules showed impressive stability, and did not seem to be influenced by either ambient temperatures or irradiation.

3.2 Daily variation in PCE

Aside from the long-term trends of PCE, the samples also exhibited daily, or diurnal, variations in efficiency. To analyse the evolution of performance over time, the daily progression of PCE over each day was plotted as a function of the cumulative irradiation absorbed by the samples, to see if days with higher irradiation would produce different effects within the samples. Figure 4 plots the outcome of this analysis for the five perovskite sub-modules over period in question.

Figure 4: Daily changes in perovskite sub-module efficiency on 8 clear sky days measured over the period January to September 2024. The efficiency is plotted against cumulative irradiation.

What is immediately striking about Figure 4 is that over an 8-month period, the PCE of the modules — with the exception of 506R — remains constant despite changes in environmental conditions. The daily profiles are also very similar for each module; in most cases samples exhibit a slightly higher PCE in the morning which decreases at a higher rate until the samples absorbed approximately 1 kWhm⁻² of irradiation. After that point, the change in efficiency progresses linearly until the end of the day, where there is a drop-off in apparent efficiency attributed to acceptance angle effects in the modules.

With the exception of sample 506P which is unchanged, the modules show, on average, a relative decrease in efficiency of 25 to 30% over the day, and a corresponding increase overnight. Interestingly, the improvement in efficiency of sample 506R over 2024 seen in Figure 3 is also evident in this plot, and includes relatively higher starting efficiencies at the beginning of the day.

3.3 Temperature coefficients

Whereas prior measurements of single-junction perovskite modules in the field tended to yield confusing temperature coefficients including positive values [6] all five samples here showed a remarkably consistent negative open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) temperature coefficient over the complete test period. Moreover, as shown in Figure 5 below, the V_{oc} temperature coefficient was consistent across devices. Figure 5 was generated using data taken during the stable period between March and July 2024, but other than a reduced scatter, the average values are obtained consistently over the entire campaign.

Figure 5: Box and whisker plots of V_{oc} temperature coefficients obtained from the five perovskite sub-modules over the period from March – July 2024. Data were filtered to consider only irradiance levels in the band 950–1050 Wm⁻².

The results shown in Figure 5 were also confirmed with indoor tests. Sample 506R was removed from the field for measurement of temperature coefficients under controlled conditions using a solar simulator. The V_{oc} temperature coefficient was determined to be -8.7 mV/°C, which falls within a standard deviation of the outdoor results' mean. The agreement between the indoor and outdoor values is attributed to the level of exposure that the sample had undergone at the point of testing, driving the perovskite cells into a stable condition. Pristine samples kept indoors as controls did not exhibit a stable V_{oc} temperature coefficient when tested under the simulator, and the values obtained were not in agreement with field observations.

Over the first year of exposure, the long-term decrease in PCE of the perovskite modules convoluted the analysis of temperature-dependent behaviour, with different fill factor (FF), maximum power (P_{max}) and short-circuit current (I_{sc}) temperature coefficients determined at different months of the year. However, once the samples had stabilised by the second year of the campaign, it was possible to investigate these with greater confidence.

It was found that the samples exhibited a strong positive FF temperature coefficient in 2024, whereas there was no discernible effect of temperature upon the P_{max} or I_{sc} . This, in combination with the negative V_{oc} temperature coefficient, presented a paradox: normally FF and V_{oc} both reduce with increasing junction temperatures, and reduce power output accordingly.

3.4 I-V curve analyses

To unravel the paradox of why V_{oc} decreases, fill factor increases, and yet PCE remains stable with increased temperature, we examined the I-V curves obtained under steady conditions on clear sky days in 2024. First the dataset was filtered to identify measurements where irradiance was similar to within $\pm 5 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$, and then from these several curves were selected from different seasons to cover a range of junction temperatures. It should be noted that while the rear-side measurements did not necessarily match the actual junction temperature, the relative changes would have been very similar. The results of this analysis are plotted in Figure 6 for samples 506P (the most stable) and 506R (the most improved). Reverse I-Vs were selected as they are deemed to be more representative than forward traces.

In the case of 506P, we can see that after the first year of exposure, the decreased shunt resistance and increased series resistance combine to shift the maximum power point of the curve above the ‘knee’ of the I-V curve. At this point, the maximum power point is remains unaffected by changes to the series resistance. Furthermore, the particular shape of the curve now results in a decrease in series resistance of the sample with increasing junction temperature. The cause of this is uncertain, but could be attributed to improved ion mobility at higher temperatures. It is also notable that both the I_{sc} and P_{max} are apparently unaffected by changes to the junction temperature, in agreement with the overall PCE trends.

Figure 6: Selected I-V characteristic curves of sample 506P (above) at 900 Wm^{-2} and 506R at 945 Wm^{-2} , taken at different junction temperatures in 2024.

In the case of sample 506R, we see that the improved performance seen in Figure 3 is linked to a recovery in the current generation of the samples over time. This sample also exhibits the same effects of temperature upon the open-circuit voltage, though in this case the performance recovery increases the P_{max} over time. Although it appears as though the device exhibits a positive I_{sc} and P_{max} temperature coefficient, this is an artefact caused by the general increase in performance over time, and is not supported by the wider dataset. It is also noteworthy that the maximum power point voltage does not vary between these measurements.

4 ANALYSIS

4.1 Performance Summary

Indoor measurements of the bare, single-junction bifacial TOPCON cell showed that the 20% efficient cell was reduced to 16% when encapsulated in the module, and that the efficiency was the same when measured from either side. When the module was mounted on the OTF test rack, the reflectance of the mounting structure was found to contribute a PCE boost of around 5% of the front-side irradiance. This resulted in a total apparent PCE of approximately 21%. Indoor measurements also established that the PCE of the front side was reduced to 8% when the perovskite layer was introduced on top of it.

In total, the starting efficiency of the better-performing tandem sample was approximately 26%, which was the combination of the pristine perovskite module and the bifacial silicon subcell. At the end of the 20 months of testing the overall efficiency had returned to 21%, which is the same as the base case of a single silicon subcell. However, over the entire campaign this tandem device delivered an overall energy conversion efficiency of 22%, and at this point the efficiency is still increasing.

Figure 7: Power conversion efficiency balance for the tandem modules. In the case of the better performing devices, the tandem structure outperforms a base-case bifacial device after 20 months of exposure.

4.2 Performance evolution

The general evolution of the PCE of this batch of mini modules shows an initial decrease in the perovskite performance over time that is attributed to the formation of ionic barriers at the layer interfaces. These act to reduce the current generation over time. However, after a full year of field exposure, it appears that this barrier formation had concluded, and the devices showed stable performance after that point. In the case of two of the modules, particularly 506R, there seems to have been some reversal of this ionic barrier formation that saw an increase in the current generation once more, and a corresponding increase in PCE over time.

The change in behaviour of the samples with temperature during the second year of exposure is consistent with the expectation that higher temperatures will reduce the apparent series resistance of samples due to the increase in ion mobility and the higher thermal energy of charge carriers, enabling them to cross over the potential barrier. In this case, the particular shape of the I-V curves showed that it was possible for this reduction to occur in a manner that did not affect the maximum power point, thus explaining the absence of a power temperature coefficient.

8 CONCLUSIONS

The combination of long-term field exposure and filtering for steady measurement conditions has allowed bifacial perovskite-on-silicon tandem mini modules to be studied under stabilised conditions. The outcome of these analyses shows that over the 20 months of outdoor exposure the tandem arrangement has provided a net increase in energy yield compared to a base case of a bifacial silicon photovoltaic module.

Somewhat surprisingly, some of the stabilised modules continue to show an increasing PCE, and have also reached a state where they show no change in efficiency with temperature.

These results provide encouragement that perovskite-on-silicon tandem modules are both technically viable and energetically advantageous, and can offer a compelling route for the incorporation of perovskite photovoltaics into mature commercial photovoltaic markets.

[1] M. A. Green *et al.*, “Solar cell efficiency tables (version 62).” *Prog. Photovoltaics Res. Appl.*, vol. 31, no. 7, pp. 651–663, 2023, doi: 10.1002/pip.3726.

[2] H. Zhang, X. Qiao, Y. Shen, and M. Wang, “Effect of temperature on the efficiency of organometallic perovskite solar cells,” *J. Energy Chem.*, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 729–735, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.jechem.2015.10.007.

[3] A. K. Mishra and R. K. Shukla, “Effect of humidity in the perovskite solar cell,” *Mater. Today Proc.*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 836–838, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2020.04.872.

[4] M. De Bastiani *et al.*, “Toward Stable Monolithic Perovskite/Silicon Tandem Photovoltaics: A Six-Month Outdoor Performance Study in a Hot and Humid Climate,” *ACS Energy Lett.*, vol. 6, pp. 2944–2951, 2021, doi: 10.1021/acsenerylett.1c01018.

[5] J. Liu *et al.*, “28.2%-Efficient, Outdoor-Stable Perovskite/Silicon Tandem Solar Cell,” *Joule*, vol. 5, no. 12, pp. 3169–3186, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.joule.2021.11.003.

[6] E. Vellilla, D. Ramirez, J. I. Uribe, J. F. Montoya, and F. Jaramillo, “Outdoor performance of perovskite solar technology: Silicon comparison and competitive advantages at different irradiances,” *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells*, vol. 191, pp. 15–20, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.solmat.2018.10.018.

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